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Isocyanide-based multicomponent reactions in the synthesis of heterocycles

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Abstract

In this review, we update our previous presentation, underscoring the recent applications of isocyanides as privileged synthons in the synthesis of various heterocyclic compounds, especially focused on those synthesized via multicomponent reactions.

Keyword

Cyanides, Heterocycles, Heterocyclic compound, Isocyanides, Multi-component reactions, Synthons, Synthesis (chemical)